

TALLINN UNIVERSITY

HUMBOLDT-UNIVERSITÄT
ZU BERLIN

Language Choice in Multilingually Diverse Settings in Austria, Estonia, Hungary and Germany: a Comparative Sociolinguistic Study of Sign Language Attitudes

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GLOBALISING SOCIOLINGUISTICS 3: LANGUAGE AND INEQUALITY - TLU - 22.-24.8.2024

Research in Sociolinguistics of Sign Languages

Multilingualism and Multimodality (Fenlon & Wilkinson 2015, Kusters 2017)

Language Contact and Tranlanguaging (Quinto-Pozos 2002, Adam 2012, Machado 2023, Kusters et al 2017)

Language Choice/Attitude (Krausneker 2015, Hill 2012, Kusters et al 2022, Rowley & Cormier 2022)

Language Rights & Recognition (Krausneker 2008, De Meulder 2015, Venade de Sousa 2023)

Endangered Languages, Language Revitalization and Language Death (Zeshan De Los 2012, Adam 2017, Braithwaite 2019)

Language Standardization and Planning (Adam 2015, Quadros & Rathmann 2021)

Global Communication (Moriarty & Kusters 2021, Kusters 2021, Rathmann & Quadros 2022)

Language Teaching / Interpreting / Translation (Stone, Adam, Quadros & Rathmann 2022)

Two objectives:

**(a) Better understanding of multilingual sign language communities in terms of sign language choice/attitude at local, regional & global levels - with focus on **

(b) Better understanding of the relationship between sign language choice/attitude and sign language inequality at local, regional and global levels.

Structure

1. Sign Language Background Information:

2. Research Design

3. Key Findings

4. Discussion and Next Steps

Urban multilingualism

Regional Sign Languages

Non-Indigenous Minority Sign Languages

Border Sign Languages

Sign Language Education

Sign Language Interpreting Services

Urban multilingualism

Regional Sign Languages

Non-Indigenous Minority Sign Languages

Border Sign Languages

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Urban multilingualism

Regional Sign Languages

Non-Indigenous Minority Sign Languages

Border Sign Languages

Sign Language Education

Sign Language Interpreting Services

International SL

American SL (ASL)

English

Sign Language Education

Sign Language Interpreting Services

2. Research Design

1. Observation

2. Explorative Expert Interviews

- Design, Pretest and Translation

- Data Collection, Annotation and Quality Content Analysis

3. Survey / Questionnaire

- Design, Pretest and Translation
- Data Collection and Quantitative Analysis

- => Sign language choices of signers with multiple sign languages with focus on major and minority sign languages in
- => Sign language choices in social media with focus on use of local sign language, IntSL & ASL in
- => Sign Language choices in formal settings with focus on language contact with neighboring sign/spoken languages in
- => Sign language choices in international/global settings with focus on language contact with Eng, IntSL & ASL in

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices of signers with multiple sign languages with focus on major and minority sign languages in 🇪🇪 🇮🇹 🇦🇹 and 🇩🇪

„Estonian sign language is in a fairly good state. It bothers me a bit when Estonian sign language gets mixed with other sign languages. There is no clear distinction, and it is still debated where the border is. There is no language monitoring mechanism here.“

3. Key Findings

⇒ Sign language choices of signers with multiple sign/written languages with focus on major and minority sign languages in 🇪🇺 🇮🇹 🇷🇺 and 🇩🇪

„There are people who don't care if their Estonian is not very good and they still write incorrectly in public. They don't care and these are the brave people.“

„If there is a way to express yourself in Russian Sign Language, then they put Estonian Sign Language aside. It is a pity. I understand that the right to use one's own language must be respected, but this has its pros and cons.“

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices of signers with multiple sign/written languages with focus on major and minority sign languages in 🇪🇪 🇮🇹 🇷🇺 and 🇩🇪

„If American signs find their way into Estonian Sign Language, I don't see it as a dangerous trend. I think it is a dangerous trend when Russian Sign Language gets into Estonian Sign Language.“

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices of signers with multiple sign/written languages with focus on major and minority sign languages in

"There are a number of sign language communities in metropolitan areas - like in Berlin with Russian SL, Ukrainian SL, Polish SL, Turkish SL, ASL and IntSL. There are two language-based associations that are members of the Berlin Deaf Association: Polish SL and Ukrainian SL. Turkish signers tend to use German SL (DGS). ASL/IntSL signers rarely have contact with DGS."

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices in social media => with focus on the use of local sign language, IntSL and ASL in 🇸🇮 🇭🇺 🇦🇹 and 🇩🇪

„It depends on who the videos are for. If it's only Austria-wide, then I sign in ÖGS. If it doesn't matter who sees it, then in International Sign.”

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices in social media => with focus on the use of local sign language, IntSL and ASL in 🇸🇮 🇭🇺 🇸🇰 and 🇩🇪

„Many children, many adults, and many elderly people have barriers. They are very frustrated because there are more and more international sign languages. It's all become a goulash soup! There is no one to keep Hungarian sign language in check, to show the way by keeping it within a unified framework. Sign language has become prey to everyone.”

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices in social media with focus on the use of local sign language, IntSL and ASL in 🇧🇪 🇮🇹 🇦🇹 and 🇩🇪

„It looks like that there are three groups: signers who use DGS, signers who use IntSL and signers with unconsciously mixed DGS and IntSL. We need to enhance awareness on the separate use of DGS and IntSL. IntSL as a school subject needs to be introduced.“

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices in formal settings with focus on language contact with neighboring sign/spoken languages in 🇪🇪 🇮🇪 🇮🇹 and 🇩🇪

“[I:] Would it bother you to see: a Russian sign language interpreter and an Estonian sign language interpreter at an event?”

[P:] Now I would accept the situation, in the past it has bothered me.”

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices in formal settings with focus on language contact with neighboring sign/spoken languages in 🇫🇮 🇮🇪 🇦🇹 and 🇩🇪

„It depends. For example, at the conference, I often prefer to use International Sign Language rather than Hungarian SL because the interpreter is not the best. S/he’s not the most accurate, but International Sign language Interpreting is usually accurate.“

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices in formal settings with focus on language contact with neighboring sign/spoken languages in 🇫🇮 🇮🇹 🇸🇰 and 🇩🇪

„There are Deaf gatherings with international guests. We often have interpreters for DGS/German and IntSL/DGS. If the events are targeted to Russians or Ukrainians, we tend to have interpreters for DGS/Ukrainian SL or DGS/Russian SL. Other languages are invisible.“

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices in international/global settings with focus on language contact with English, IntSL and ASL in 🇧🇪 🇮🇹 🇷🇺 and 🇩🇪

„The best way for me to express myself is in Estonian sign language, which I respect. I do use Russian sign language, more to help others, and I rarely use American Sign Language. I tend to use American Sign Language more for social media, such as Facebook, and elsewhere abroad. There is little use of American Sign Language in Estonia.“

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices in international/global settings with focus on language contact with English, IntSL and ASL in 🇸🇪 🇮🇹 🇦🇹 and 🇩🇪

„Sometimes there are situations where I think it's better to express myself in International Sign, because then everyone can understand it, no matter who it is.”

3. Key Findings

=> Sign language choices in international/global settings with focus on language contact with English, IntSL and ASL in 🇸🇪 🇮🇹 🇷🇺 and 🇩🇪

„I see from experience that more and more people are using, and fewer and fewer older people and more and more young people are using International Sign Language. This is very positive and it is due to social media.””

3. Key Findings

3. Preliminary Findings (Survey - Pretest)

WHAT IS THE LANGUAGE THAT YOU USE MOST OFTEN NOW?
(N=10)

WHAT LANGUAGE IS MOST COMMONLY USED IN YOUR COMMUNITY NOW? (N=10)

=> Multilingual Situation in Estonian Sign Language Communities

3. Preliminary Findings (Survey - Pretest)

"It is not a problem if I see other signers use signs from other sign languages in conversation."
(1 - I strongly disagree; 5 - I strongly agree, n=10)

Have you ever experienced that it is better if you do not sign now because it feels bad?
(1 - I strongly disagree; 5 - I strongly agree, n=10)

=> Language Choice / Attitude in Estonian Sign Language Communities

4. Discussion and Next Steps

4.1. Multilingual sign language communities

in terms of sign language choice/attitude at local, regional & global levels => an emerging research topic

4.2. Correlation between sign language choice/attitude and sign language inequality

- Sign Language Contact / Translanguaging
- Sign Language Diglossic Situation / SL Prestige
- Sign Language Endangerment
- Status of Sign Languages as Minority Languages
- Sign Language Ideology

4. Discussion and **Next Steps**

(i) Data Analysis (Interviews and Surveys)

(ii) Laurimaa's PhD Project at Tallinn University: Use of Sign Language Interpreting Services and Language Needs of SLI Service Users in Estonia 🇪🇺

(iii) Language Demographics / Portraits in

(iv) Unlocking Sign Language Learning Opportunities

=> DeafSign Project at ECML

(v) Language Planning

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